

RUSSIAN HOUSE AS A PHENOMENON OF MATERIAL AND SPIRITUAL CULTURE

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Before humanity began to design and build multi-story buildings in which not one family, but many people could live, man had come a very long way. At the beginning of his development, Man found a cave, managed to make a fire, and shelter in it from the rain and heat. Then, a person gradually builds a house in a more convenient practical form, managing to drag fire there and imprison it in the walls of his house to preserve heat for a longer time. People managed to survive and build their homes, taking into account a number of certain factors. These are natural resources and climatic conditions. The construction of a house was accompanied not only by material needs, but also by the emergence and observance of various rituals and superstitions.

The article examines the “Russian National House”. The relevance of this publication lies in the fact that the Russian house continues to exist and interest in it does not disappear at all. Every person strives to escape from city life and retire to nature, go to the countryside or out of town to the country. However, the twenty-first century and the way of such familiar life adjust the convenience of the Russian home. There are now Russian house-hotels. This is nothing more than an opportunity for a person to find himself in a hotel, the room for which is stylized not only externally, but also internally in the form of a full-fledged “Russian national house” with the surrounding beautiful and incredible nature and all other necessary conditions.

The interest in this work lies in identifying the original, real, real inner world of the Russian national house, which was created by the Russian people throughout

the history of its existence. Many people think that building a Russian house is very simple. However, before they began to build it, people went through a huge stage in the history of their lives. The construction of the Russian national house was influenced by many factors [5].

Nature determined almost everything for the Russian people: the choice of life near the river; ability to build simple houses; come up with a stove for heat and place it correctly in the house for a more convenient exit of smoke; getting food in the forest (hunting and picking berries) and obtaining the necessary building material (wood). The forest provided Russian people with various services. These could be for economic needs, the opportunity to hunt, and the forest was an excellent defense against enemies [5].

The negative aspects of the forest were that there were predators and robbers in it. The forest grew and had to be cut down or even burned, as it threatened the crops. The steppe was completely uncomfortable for the settled life of people. Taking into account all these factors, a Russian house is created [5].

The scientist Kostomarov wrote that the houses were quadrangular and wooden. They were made from pine or solid oak beams. They folded the beams with great skill, according to the remarks of foreigners, so tightly that there was not a single one left for the passage of air, and without using a single nail in the whole house... Completely thick beams were held tightly together, and for warmth they were also covered with moss; Moss was placed on the doors and windows. It was called building a house in moss [6].

According to another scientist whose last name is Belov, we can find the following: “Building a house can be compared to painting icons. The art of the painter and carpenter has nourished the origins of Russian culture since ancient times. There are no identical icons for the same subject, although each of them should have something obligatory for everyone. The same thing with houses... The winter house was called a “house for winter”, it was also built in different ways. But if it doesn’t have either a large stove or benches, then it’s no longer a “house for winter,” but something else” [1].

Remembering our time and making a small digression, it should be said that when it comes to the Russian hut, it is essentially a peasant dwelling. “House for winter” was only a variety, and another name usually meant some kind of functional changes, much like in our time high-rise buildings are also called differently, depending not so much on the functionality, but, for example, on the time of construction : Stalinka, Khrushchev, or type of construction: panels, monoliths, etc., or option of settlement: communal apartment. All these names defined a person’s home.

Every person dreams of warmth in his or her home. If a person brought a fire home, there would be a fire. Therefore, they learned to contain fire in stalls. The oven itself was made of clay or brick. Its location could determine many things: convenience for the hostess and the rest of the environment. In the opposite corner, diagonally, was the Red Corner. There was a table and icons were placed on a shelf. The second corner in the hut was considered the most important and bright. Although the corner with the stove was the warmest, the energy there was dark [2].

Benches and tables could be covered with carpets. The same thing happened with the walls. More often, they were hung with paintings containing biblical scenes. There were no mirrors or clocks in the house. The scientist Belov wrote that if we consider all household items, we would need to write several volumes [1].

Russia is a waterpower. However, there were small problems here too. Therefore, for example, the scientist Boris Fedorovich Yegorov wrote about this that in the village they carried water themselves: from the river, from the lake, from the well. They carried water in buckets, but it took a lot of strength to drag the water for a long time and get it out. In other words, in the world's most water-rich country, water delivery has proven to be a major problem [4].

Growing berries in their own garden, rather than picking them in the forest, was completely absent from ordinary peasants living in the village. Sweet treats were extremely rare on the table. Due to the almost complete absence of gardens, due to the collection of fruits and berries only in the forests, and because of the

economy of sugar, little jam was made: honey, due to the small number of peasant forests and apiaries, was also a holiday, and not an everyday delicacy [4].

Every person living in any part of Russia will want his home to be a holy place and protected not only physically, i.e. fenced with a fence, etc., but also sacredly protected from evil spirits. In this regard, the Russian person strives to create a Small Church from his home. Moreover, for this to happen, the house must be consecrated and equipped with icons [3]. Prayers were read constantly. They prayed when they woke up and when they started doing something. To the question posed: “Was it necessary or was there a need to read the prayers specifically out loud?” – we do not receive an exact answer and information regarding this significant issue differs from each other. Behavior at the table and observance of fasting in a peasant family were the strictest of all that could be. Russian people believed that there was an angel standing at the table. It was forbidden to quarrel, sit, and dangle your legs, dip bread in a saltshaker, etc. In many ways, the understanding of “what a family is and what it should be” played a big role. A single lifestyle was considered a deviation and strangeness at a time when the family was perceived as the economic and moral basis of a correct lifestyle. In various sources, you can find that an unmarried person could not be recognized as a true peasant. Such a person will be looked at only with one great regret. Society prohibits a single person from being the owner of his own home. The head of a peasant family, in all regions of Russia, will be a man. All family members recognized the supremacy of a particular man. According to custom, the eldest of the men became the head. However, the transfer of these rights to another member of the family is not excluded. Usually women heated stoves, milked cows, fed livestock, and looked after poultry. The man's substitute could be a woman's mother-in-law [3].

As the study showed, the Russian house could not appear out of nowhere. A number of factors that lined up one after another accompanied this.

Based on all of the above, we understand that a Russian hut for a peasant is not just a house consisting of four walls, a stove and other amenity. For a person, a house was not only a refuge, but also a small church.

If for us now a Russian hut is just an external appearance and interior, then previously it was a completely built world, the patterns of which were built over a long time and preserved for centuries.

Reference:

1. Белов В. И. «Лад. Очерки народной эстетики». – М.: Институт русской цивилизации, 2013. – 512 с.
2. Беловинский Л. В. «История русской материальной культуры». – М.: Издательское предприятие «Вузовская книга», 2003. – 424 с.
3. Громыко М. М., Буганов А. В. «О воззрениях русского народа». – М.: Издательство «Паломникъ», 2000. – 544 с.
4. Егоров Б. Ф. «Из истории русской культуры», том V (XIX век). – М.: «Языки русской культуры», 1996. – 848 с.
5. Ключевский В. О. «Курс русской истории. Собрание в девяти томах». – М.: Издательство «Мысль», 1987. – 430 с.
6. Костомаров Н. И. «Домашняя жизнь и нравы великорусского народа». – М.: Издательство «Экономика», 1993. – 399 с.